

User study for Jupyter4NFDI report

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Study objective

Base4NFDI integrates and establishes basic services as common, interoperable solutions for the NFDI. Base4NFDI includes 4 different task areas. Task area 2 aims to provide usability evaluations for different services in order to assist the ramp up process for the services. Jupyter4NFDI aims to address the fragmented deployment of Jupyter Notebooks across NFDI consortia by offering a centralized service. This service will simplify access, improve user experience, and extend Jupyter's reach to a wider audience within and beyond the NFDI. Currently Jupyter4NFDI is in the initialization phase, adding in different functionalities with each new update.

Google Colab is a free-to-use version of Jupyter Notebook offered by Google which allows users to execute python code in the cloud on the web browser. Compared to the functionality provided by traditional Jupyter Notebooks, Google Colab provides fewer functionalities but focuses on ease-of-use and low entry requirements. The objective of this study was to evaluate the usability and functionality of Google Colab in comparison to Jupyter4NFDI, with a focus on assessing their effectiveness in supporting data analysis workflows. Specifically, the study aimed to identify common challenges and limitations encountered by users when working with each platform, highlighting areas that may require improvements or optimizations. Additionally, user feedback was collected to gain insights into the overall user experience, including ease of use, feature accessibility, and the intuitiveness of each tool. By analyzing participants' interactions and qualitative feedback, the study sought to provide actionable recommendations for enhancing the usability and efficiency of these computational notebooks.

Method

Participants were recruited through institutional mailing lists and the Jupyter4NFDI project survey, yielding a final sample of seven individuals. Participants were all researchers or data scientists who have regular interaction with handling large datasets. All study sessions were conducted remotely via video conferencing software to ensure accessibility and consistency across participants. At the start of each session, a researcher provided a detailed introduction to the study's objectives and procedures, after which participants were required to review and sign an informed consent form.

Each participant was assigned two data analysis tasks, which involved working with either Jupyter or Google Colab. For each task, participants were provided with a predefined dataset and were instructed to systematically perform data importation, cleaning, analysis, and visualization using the assigned platform. They were encouraged to articulate their thought processes, reasoning, and challenges encountered in real time while completing these steps. This think-aloud protocol was employed to gain insights into participants' cognitive strategies, tool usability, and decision-making processes throughout the data analysis workflow. After each session, participants completed an interview about their experience. The whole session lasted approximately one hour.

Summary of results

Users generally found Jupyter notebooks to be a better fit for their needs, reinforcing its viability both as a use case and as the foundation for the implementation of Jupyter4NFDI. However, several features from Google Colab were also identified as potentially valuable additions or future directions for Jupyter4NFDI. The most frequently mentioned feature was Colab's AI integration with Gemini, which users recognized as particularly useful. While many users already use ChatGPT alongside Jupyter, the direct integration of AI within the system allows for in-context assistance, streamlining workflows and enhancing the overall user experience. Despite this advantage, users also expressed concerns regarding AI implementation, particularly in relation to data privacy, with specific apprehension about Google's involvement. This highlights a strong incentive for Jupyter4NFDI to incorporate AI in a way that prioritizes data privacy while maintaining its research-oriented focus.

In addition to AI integration, users frequently praised Google Colab's collaboration features, which facilitate seamless teamwork and knowledge exchange. While Jupyter4NFDI serves as a central hub for researchers, further enhancements in collaboration capabilities could significantly improve interdisciplinary engagement and user involvement. Strengthening collaboration tools within Jupyter4NFDI would not only increase its accessibility but also foster a more interactive and cooperative research environment.

Lastly, users noted that the log-in and accessibility process for Jupyter4NFDI could benefit from improvements, particularly through the upcoming integration of IAM4NFDI. Currently, the sign-up and authentication process is perceived as somewhat cumbersome and confusing. The adoption of IAM4NFDI could streamline and simplify access, making it more user-friendly while maintaining necessary security measures. Addressing these concerns would further enhance Jupyter4NFDI's usability and appeal to a broader range of researchers.

Results

Login Process

Users reported that the login process for Jupyter can be confusing, particularly when requiring authentication through institutional credentials. Some users struggled to find the correct institution, and in some cases, the login process failed or was unclear. This presents a barrier for researchers who rely on quick and easy access to their work environments. Since Jupyter often operates through institutional or private servers, users sometimes have to navigate multiple steps or permissions before gaining access. This complexity may deter some users, particularly those who are not accustomed to institutional authentication systems.

Conversely, Google Colab offers a more seamless login experience, particularly with the option to use a Google account. This makes it accessible to a broader audience, including those without institutional credentials. The ability to log in with a Google account reduces friction and allows users to quickly access their work without dealing with complex authentication steps. This ease of access is particularly beneficial for students, independent researchers, and those working outside structured institutional environments. By simplifying the login process, Google Colab ensures that users can focus more on their research and less on administrative hurdles.

Handling Complex Tasks and Large Datasets

While Google Colab was highly accessible and easy to use, Jupyter was preferred for handling complex tasks and large datasets due to its flexibility and computational power. Most users also gave Jupyter a higher rating than Google Colab when asked about their experience and likelihood to recommend the tool to a colleague, citing mostly the availability of advanced possibilities that Jupyter offers compared to Colab.

- One user stated, *“Use Jupyter if you have a machine, which is capable of running big data sets. If not, yeah, always Google Colab.”* - U5.

This emphasizes how Jupyter is often the preferred choice for users working with large-scale data processing, provided they have the necessary hardware. Colab’s cloud-based resources may not always be sufficient for handling computationally intensive tasks.

- Another user added, *“Since it has the other pages on Jupyter for example, the more advanced features that we did not use this time, but for example there is the GPUs and the other performance hardware.”* - U6.

This highlights Jupyter’s capability to integrate with more advanced hardware configurations, such as GPUs, making it the better choice for machine learning and high-performance computing tasks.

AI Functionality in Google Colab

Google Colab integrates AI assistance, specifically through Gemini, which users found beneficial. However, users also noted limitations in its effectiveness depending on the specificity of the query. The AI integration in Colab is prominently displayed, making it easily accessible for users who need assistance while coding.

- **Ease of Use and Accessibility:**

- One user mentioned, *“I can also see Gemini displayed up here in a friendly manner, maybe there's already an AI chatbot with the simple model. That might also help a lot more in terms of not having to run GPT on the second screen at the same time, if Gemini could basically answer all of these questions.”* - U1.

This quote highlights the potential of AI tools within Colab to streamline workflows. The user appreciates the convenience of having AI assistance embedded directly in the platform rather than needing to run a separate AI tool on another screen. This integration reduces the need for context switching, allowing users to remain focused on their work without disruptions.

- Another user noted, *“Yes, and here [Colab] Gemini is of course advertised straight away, you can see it up there with the thing, it's clear. As I said, it's of course really convenient to look at these recommended diagrams and so on, it's really nice.”* - U2.

This statement emphasizes how AI-powered recommendations, such as visual representations and diagrams, can enhance the coding experience. The presence of AI-driven insights may help users better understand their data and coding tasks.

- *“On the other hand the way it comes up to help with you, say for example here it could use some help and also when you try to complete the code and it straight away gives you lots of recommendations.”* - U7.

- **Limitations:**

- While users find AI integration helpful, they also highlight its shortcomings. One user stated, *“I have to say I'm a bit torn. On the one hand, it's really practical when you can just type something in and it spits out the code. On the other hand, I've tried it out for a few things and the more unspecific or less I know in principle what has to happen to the data and how in order to get to a certain path, the more error-prone the whole thing is. And I've had tests where I just said I'd like to do this and that, but it was relatively vague and it just didn't work at all.”* - U2.

This quote reveals the challenge of relying on AI-generated code, particularly when the user is unclear about the exact steps needed. While AI can generate useful code snippets, its effectiveness diminishes when given vague or ambiguous instructions. This suggests that AI assistance is most valuable when users already have a foundational understanding of their coding tasks and can provide precise prompts.

Accessibility and Usability

Google Colab is often recommended for users with limited technical knowledge or without access to Jupyter environments. Users appreciate its accessibility, particularly for those who do not have the necessary hardware or permissions to set up a Jupyter environment. The online possibility that Jupyter4NFDI provides alleviates the problem with machine and hardware requirements. However, JupyterHubs often require institutional access in order to be used. However, Jupyter4NFDI provides the possibility of access through Google and GitHub, which expands on its accessibility.

- One user explained, *“If you have no idea how to get it onto your computer, if you don't have any prerequisites or permissions that would let you access a Jupyter Hub, try Colab. It depends on the person, what I would recommend, that's how I would put it.”* - U3.

This highlights how Google Colab serves as an ideal solution for users who lack the technical expertise or necessary system permissions to configure a local Jupyter environment.

- Another user remarked, *“And most of my students also use Google Colab, because it's very easy to use. You don't have to depend on anything.”* - U5.

The simplicity and independence of Colab make it particularly appealing in educational settings, where ease of use and accessibility are critical.

- Similarly, another user remarked: *“The speed of Jupyter Notebook needs to be a little bit faster. It's sometimes it's quite slow. The interface needs to change a little bit to be more modern. It's very old style. I think sometimes I really am confused about navigation of the Jupyter notebook. It keeps opening new tabs, so sometimes I lose which tab I'm in.”* - U7

This user highlighted the perceived outdatedness of the user interface of Jupyter, which could potentially harm the usability of the application.

Collaboration

Collaboration features in Google Colab were highlighted as a major advantage over Jupyter. Users appreciated the ability to share notebooks and collaborate in real time.

- One user commented, *“That's why it's moving towards doing it in a cloud. What I don't know is that I see a share notebook on Google Colab, which is pretty cool. I assume I can share it with someone and work on it at the same time, right? A group of some sort, maybe one after the other. That's pretty cool. I didn't see that on Jupyter.”* - U4.

This demonstrates how Google Colab's cloud-based nature facilitates seamless collaboration, allowing multiple users to work on a project simultaneously. This feature is particularly useful for team-based research projects and classroom environments where students or colleagues need to work together in real time.

Recommendations

- Incorporate AI assistance directly within Jupyter4NFDI, but ensure it aligns with research data privacy standards. Explore deploying on-premise or open-source models (e.g., open LLMs) to maintain data sovereignty and user trust.
- Prioritize and streamline the integration of IAM4NFDI to simplify authentication. Ensure a clear, user-friendly login flow with intuitive institution selection and fallback options (e.g., GitHub, Google login) to support broader accessibility.
- Introduce robust collaboration capabilities within Jupyter4NFDI, such as live editing, comment threads, version control, and seamless sharing, to foster teamwork and interdisciplinary engagement.
- Develop interactive tutorials, guided walkthroughs, and tooltips tailored to novice users. Provide quick-start templates and explainers to ease new users into Jupyter4NFDI's advanced functionalities. Organize online workshops to onboard the users.